

Update on Ocean Energy Systems- Environmental: what we know and still need to know about environmental effects of marine energy

Andrea Copping, Lysel Garavelli, Lenaig Hemery, Mikaela Freeman, Hayley Farr
Pacific Northwest National Laboratory

Marine energy technologies are becoming more robust and efficient, resource characterization of tides, waves, currents, and thermal gradients is increasingly pinpointing hotspots for energy generation, and the policy landscape for offshore renewables is becoming clearer. These advances create increased urgency to ensure that devices and systems can be deployed and operated without harm to the marine environment. The very best turbines or WECs will never operate if they cannot be permitted, licensed, and deployed.

OES-Environmental is a collaboration among 16 nations that seeks to understand and resolve the risks to the marine environment from the development and operation of marine energy devices, with the intent of accelerating deployment of devices in a responsible manner. The task publishes its State of the Science report every four years, with the 2024 edition to be released in September 2024. The State of the Science brings together up-to-date research on potential risks to marine animals, habitats, oceanographic processes, and the marine ecosystem from the development of marine energy.

Ocean Energy Systems (OES) is a technology collaboration program under the International Energy Agency, convening nations with an interest in the development of marine energy. OES-Environmental is the longest running task under OES, led by the United States (U.S.) Department of Energy, in collaboration with other U.S. federal agencies, and implemented by Pacific Northwest National Laboratory.

This poster will provide updates on the status of research into environmental effects of marine energy, as collated and integrated by OES-Environmental.